

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF PYRENE

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A new synthesis of pyrene is described in the present communication.

A new synthesis of pyrene which will be an useful supplement to the existing methods (Weitzenbock, *Monatsh.*, 1913, 34, 193; Freund and Fleischer, *Annalen*, 1914, 402, 77; Fleischer and Retze, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 3280; Braun and Rath, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 956; Cook *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 365) and which will be useful in the synthesis of pyrene derivatives having carcinogenic activity is described in the present communication.

Diethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate* (I, $R_1 = R-H$; $R_2 = CO_2Et$; $R_3 = CH_2.CO_2Et$) obtained from ethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate* and ethyl chloroacetate is transformed by boiling alcoholic sodium ethoxide into ethyl 6-carbethoxy*cyclohexanone-2-acetate* (I, $R = R_2 = H$; $R_1 = CO_2Et$; $R_3 = CH_2.CO_2Et$), the mechanism being obviously alcoholysis and ring-closure in a new position. A second acetic acid residue is then introduced in the usual manner to yield diethyl 6-carbethoxy*cyclohexanone-2:6-diacetate* (I, $R_1 = R_3 = CH_2.CO_2Et$; $R = CO_2Et$; $R_2 = H$). This ester on hydrolysis yields *cyclohexanone-2:6-diacetic acid* (I, $R_1 = R_2 = H$; $R = R_3 = CH_2.COOH$). It is esterified and treated with phenyl magnesium bromide when diethyl 1-phenyl*cyclohexanol-2:6-diacetate* (III) is obtained. The above ester on dehydration and dehydrogenation yields diethyl diphenyl-2:6-diacetate (IV, $R = R_1 = Et$). Diphenyl-2:6-diacetic acid (IV, $R = R_1 = H$), obtained on hydrolysing the above ester, yields a gummy product on ring-closure. Pyrene (V) is obtained from this gummy product on distillation with zinc dust.

For the synthesis of ethyl 6-carbethoxy*cyclohexanone-2-acetate* by another method, diethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate* is treated with sodium ethoxide when ethyl hexane-1:2:6-tricarboxylate (II) is obtained (corresponding acid is obtained on hydrolysis). When this ester is treated with sodium in benzene, the desired ester (I, $R = R_3 = H$; $R_1 = CO_2Et$; $R_3 = CH_2.CO_2Et$) is obtained in poor yield. The ester (I, $R_1 = R_3 = CH_2.CO_2Et$; $R = CO_2Et$; $R_2 = H$) is also

obtained from ester (II) in poor yield by Dieckmann reaction and subsequent treatment with ethyl chloroacetate.

The synthesis of methylpyrenes by the above process is in progress and will be communicated in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate.—(i). Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (25 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (3.4 g.) in alcohol (31 c.c.) and the solid sodium salt was heated under reflux for 6 hours with ethyl chloroacetate (19 g.). After dilution the condensation product was extracted with ether, the ether removed and the product distilled at 168-175°/11 mm., yield 18 g.

(ii). A solution of sodium ethoxide from sodium (3.4 g.) in alcohol (33 c.c.) was slowly added with shaking to a mixture of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (25 g.) and bromoacetic ester (26 g.), absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and sodium iodide (0.3 g.), with cooling in a bath of ice-cold water. The reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 2 hours, and after refluxing for further 2 hours, the greater part of alcohol was evaporated. The residue was poured in ice-water (1000 c.c.) and the precipitated oil isolated by means of ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed, and it was then distilled, b. p. 168-175°/11 mm., yield 20 g.

(iii). Finely divided metallic sodium (3.4 g.) in dry benzene (120 c.c.) was slowly treated with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (25 g.) and kept overnight. Ethyl chloroacetate (19 g.) was then added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 6 hours. It was then cooled, washed with water, dried over calcium

chloride and the benzene removed. The residual oil distilled at 168-175°/11 mm., yield 24 g. (Found : C, 60.9 ; H, 7.76. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}O_5$: C, 60.9 ; H, 7.8 per cent).

Ethyl Hexane-1 : 2 : 6-tricarboxylate.—Diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (27 g.) was mixed with sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.5 g. and absolute alcohol, 11 c.c.) and heated on the water-bath for 2½ hours. The cooled solution was poured into a mixture of ether and water, and ethereal extract separated, washed with water and dried and the ether removed. The triethyl ester had b. p. 183°/8 mm., yield 21 g. (Found : C, 59.7 ; H, 8.32. $C_{15}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 59.6 ; H, 8.6 per cent).

Hexane-1 : 2 : 6-tricarboxylic Acid.—Ethyl hexane-1 : 2 : 6-tricarboxylate (10 g.) was refluxed with boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 c.c., 4 hours) and the acid isolated by removal of the mineral acid under reduced pressure was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether, m. p. 90°. (Found : C, 49.7 ; H, 6.8. $C_9H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 49.5 ; H, 6.4 per cent).

Ethyl 6-Carbethoxycyclohexanone-2-acetate.—Ethyl hexane-1 : 2 : 6-tricarboxylate (19 g.) was heated on the water-bath with molecular sodium (3 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.) for 1 hour to start the reaction. Heating was then continued for further 1 hour. After the addition of alcohol (10 c.c.) and water to the cooled reaction mixture, the solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, ether added, the ether separated, washed with sodium carbonate solution, then with water and dried, and the solvent removed. The keto-ester (5 g.), b. p. 169-170°/5 mm. gives a deep violet coloration with ferric chloride. (Found : C, 61.4 ; H, 7.64. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9 ; H, 7.8 per cent).

Ethyl 6-Carbethoxycyclohexanone-2-acetate.—A mixture of diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (48 g.) and alcoholic sodium ethoxide (48 g. Na and 70 c.c. alcohol) was refluxed for 8 hours on the sand-bath. The product was treated with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and extracted by means of ether and after removing the ether it was collected at 169-170°/5 mm. It gives deep violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, yield 30 g. (Found : C, 60.6 ; H, 8.1. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9 ; H, 7.8 per cent).

Diethyl 6-Carbethoxycyclohexanone-2 : 6-diacetate.—Ethyl hexane-1 : 2 : 6-tricarboxylate (23 g.) was refluxed with molecular sodium (3.5 g) for 3 hours in benzene (75 c.c.). After it was cooled, ethyl chloroacetate (20 c. c) was added and refluxing continued for 6 hours. After working up in the usual manner, it was collected at 190°/4 mm., yield 12 g. (Found : C, 59.9 ; H, 7.4. $C_{17}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 59.65 ; H, 7.6 per cent).

Diethyl 6-Carbethoxycyclohexanone-2 : 6-diacetate.—Ethyl 6-carbethoxycyclohexanone-2-acetate (48 g.) was added to a suspension of sodium powder (5.4 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.). The solution of the sodium was completed by refluxing for 2 hours. The orange liquid was cooled and ethyl chloroacetate (24 g.) introduced. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hours ; no solid, however, separated from the slightly turbid solution. The reaction product was mixed with water and a few drops of hydrochloric acid, and the ester was isolated by means of ether. The ethereal extract

was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. It was then collected at $190^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 25 g. (Found : C, 59.7 ; H, 7.42. $C_{17}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 59.65 ; H, 7.6 per cent).

cycloHexanone-2:6-diacetic Acid.—A mixture of diethyl 6-carbethoxy-*cyclohexanone-2:6-diacetate* (25 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c. c.) was refluxed for 1 hour, and the clear solution was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue crystallised and the solid was collected, washed with saturated aqueous ammonium sulphate and then with a little water, dried at 100° , and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum, m. p. 188° , yield 9 g. (Found : C, 56.46 ; H, 6.8 ; Equiv., 107. $C_{10}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 56.1 ; H, 6.54 per cent. Equiv., 107).

Diethyl cycloHexanone-2:6-diacetate.—The above acid (10 g.) was esterified by means of alcohol (50 c.c.) saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride. It was kept overnight and then refluxed for 7 hours. After dilution it was extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with sodium carbonate, water and dried. After removing ether, the di-ester was collected at $170-175^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 8 g. (Found : C, 62.4 ; H, 8.3. $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 62.2 ; H, 8.15 per cent).

Diethyl 1-Phenylcyclohexanol-2:6-diacetate.—Phenyl magnesium bromide (from 1.5 g. of magnesium and 7.5 g. of bromobenzene in 30 c.c. dry ether) was added drop by drop to a cooled ethereal solution of diethyl *cyclohexanone-2:6-diacetate* (12 g., 30 c.c. dry ether) and the mixture left overnight. The product was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and the ether removed. It was then collected at $205-215^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 3 g. (Found : C, 69.4 ; H, 7.7. $C_{20}H_{28}O_5$ requires C, 69.0 ; H, 8.0 per cent).

Diphenyl-2:6-diacetic Acid.—Diethyl 2-phenyl*cyclohexanol-2:6-diacetate* (5 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating with calculated quantity of sulphur at $200-250^{\circ}$ for 4 hours. The product was taken in ether and washed by means of alkali, and after removing the solvent it was heated in benzene solution for 4 hours in presence of precipitated copper. The resulting ester, obtained after working up in the usual manner, distilled at $200-205^{\circ}/3$ mm. It was hydrolysed by means of alcoholic potash and the acid, obtained on acidifying the alkaline solution, was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 168° . (Found : C, 71.0 ; H, 5.9. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.1 ; H, 5.18 per cent).

Pyrene.—The above acid (4 g.) was converted into its chloride by boiling with thionyl chloride (40 c.c.), excess of thionyl chloride being then removed on the water-bath under reduced pressure. An ice-cold carbon disulphide (40 c.c.) solution of the chloride was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.2 g.) kept at 0° for 3 hours. The non-acidic gummy product obtained after working up in the usual manner did not solidify when kept in a vacuum desiccator, but on distillation with zinc dust yielded pyrene, m.p. 150° (mixed m.p. 150°).